

Condensations of Furil and Furoin.

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The remarkable resemblance between benzaldehyde and furfural is further exemplified by great similarity in the chemical behaviour of benzoin and furoin as well as benzil and furil, both of which undergo exactly similar types of condensations. Thus it has been found that just like benzil furil undergoes the following condensations

(1) Furil condenses with aldehydes in presence of ammonia forming iminazoles (cf. Japp and co-workers, *J Chem Soc*, 1882, 41, 326, 1883, 43, 10, 1884, 45, 672, *et al*) and 1,0 oxazoles could be isolated though the condensations were effected at different temperatures and pressures (cf. Sircar and Guha-Roy, *J. Chem Soc*, 1925, 127, 1048, Sircar and Sen, *J Indian Chem Soc*, 1936, 13, 482) Furil condenses with salicylaldehyde and furfuraldehyde forming compounds (I) and (II) (cf. Japp, *J Chem. Soc.*, 1884, 45, 672).

(2) Furil reacts with compounds containing reactive methylene groups, *e.g.*, acetoacetic ester, cyanoacetic ester, benzyl cyanide, acetylacetone, malonic ester, phloroglucinol, hippuric acid using piperidine as the condensing agent. In each case only one of the ketonic groups of furil reacts with one molecule of the compound containing reactive methylene group, while Japp and Lander (*J Chem. Soc*, 1896, 69, 736), observed that one molecule of acetoacetic ester condenses with two molecules of benzil

(3) Furil condenses with urea and thiourea with the formation of ureine (III) and thioureine (cf. Anschutz and Geldermann, *Annalen*, 1891, 281, 129).

Similarly like benzoin furoin also undergoes condensations with
(a) primary monoamines forming indoles (IV) (*cf.* Japp and Murray, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1894, 68, 889)

(b) urea and thiourea forming iminazolone (V) and thioiminazolone.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Furil (0.5 g.) and *p*-hydroxy-benzaldehyde (0.36 g.) were heated with excess of liquor ammonia in a sealed tube at 165° for 1½ hours. The resulting precipitate was washed with alcohol and crystallised from nitrobenzene in greyish-white microscopic plates, m.p. 235-36°. It is soluble in acetic acid and nitrobenzene; insoluble in ether, benzene, alcohol, acetone, chloroform and carbon tetrachloride. It dissolves in sulphuric acid with a brown colour and in boiling caustic alkalis. (Found : N, 9.7. C₁₇H₁₂O₃N₂ requires N, 9.6 per cent).

3'-Hydroxy-2-phenylfuriliminazole was prepared in the same way as the preceding compound from furil (0.5 g.) and *m*-hydroxybenzaldehyde (0.36 g.). It crystallised from nitrobenzene in white microscopic plates, m.p. 265° (with previous blackening at 225°). It is soluble in chloroform, acetone and alcohol. (Found : N, 9.1. C₁₇H₁₂O₃N₂ requires N, 9.6 per cent).

4'-Nitro-2-phenylfuriliminazole was prepared as usual from furil (1 g.) and *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde (0.36 g.). It separated from acetone in yellow microscopic plates, m.p. 175° (with blackening at 170°). It is insoluble in ether, benzene and carbon tetrachloride, and soluble in chloroform and nitrobenzene. It dissolves in dilute acetic acid with a beautiful yellow colour. (Found : N, 13.5. C₁₇H₁₁O₄N₃ requires N, 13.1 per cent).

Condensation of Furil with Salicylaldehyde.—Through an

absolute alcoholic solution of furil (1 mol., 1.3 g.) and salicylaldehyde (2 mols., 1.8 g.) dry ammonia gas was passed until the solution was saturated. The flask was then corked and allowed to stand for 1 hour. The separated lemon-yellow rectangular crystals were filtered and repeatedly washed with hot alcohol. It is insoluble in ether, alcohol, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, acetic acid and nitrobenzene and soluble in pyridine. It does not melt up to 307°. It dissolves in caustic potash solution on long boiling, and is reprecipitated on the addition of acids. (Found: N, 7.0. $C_{24}H_{20}O_6N_2$ requires N, 6.5 per cent).

The *acetyl* derivative was prepared by heating it with 3 times its weight of acetic anhydride for 3 hours and was obtained as transparent rectangular plates, m.p. 246°. (Found N, 5.8. $C_{28}H_{24}O_8N_2$ requires N, 5.4 per cent)

Condensation of Furil with Furfuraldehyde—Dry ammonia gas was passed through the solution of furil (1 mol., 0.8 g.) and furfuraldehyde (0.9 g.) in hot absolute alcohol till it was saturated and the mixture allowed to stand overnight. The separated yellow needles were collected and washed with hot alcohol. It does not melt up to 280°. It is insoluble in any of the common organic solvents except pyridine and resembles the preceding compound in its properties. (Found N, 7.6. $C_{20}H_{16}O_6N_2$ requires N, 7.3 per cent)

Phenylcyanoethylene-desoxyfuroin—A mixture of furil (1.5 g.), benzyl cyanide (1 g.), piperidine (0.5 c.c.) and absolute alcohol (50 c.c.) was heated on the water-bath for 7 hours under reflux. The mixture, diluted with water, was mixed with sodium acetate (2 g.) when a crystalline precipitate separated. This was collected, washed with water and finally crystallised from alcohol as brown microscopic plates, not melting up to 275°. It is soluble in acetone, acetic acid and chloroform but insoluble in ether and benzene. (Found N, 4.99. $C_{18}H_{11}O_3N$ requires N, 4.8 per cent).

Benzoylamino-carboxyethylene-desoxyfuroin was prepared in the same way as the preceding compound from furil (1.5 g.) and hippuric acid (1.4 g.). It crystallised from alcohol in dark grey microscopic plates, not melting up to 265°. It is soluble in acetone, chloroform and nitrobenzene but insoluble in ether. (Found N, 3.97. $C_{19}H_{13}O_6N$ requires N, 3.9 per cent).

Cyanocarbelhoxyethylene-desoxyfuroin was prepared in the same way as the preceding compounds from furil (1.5 g.) and ethyl cyanoacetate (0.9 g.). It crystallises from acetone in brown microscopic

plates, not melting up to 255°. It is insoluble in ether but soluble in alcohol and chloroform. (Found: N, 5.11. $C_{15}H_{11}O_5N$ requires N, 4.9 per cent).

Acetylcarbethoxyethylene-desoxyfuroin, prepared from furil (1.5 g.) and ethyl acetoacetate (1.2 g.), was obtained as brown microscopic plates from alcohol, not melting up to 275°. It is soluble in acetic acid, acetone and chloroform but insoluble in benzene and ether. (Found: C, 64.0; H, 4.2. $C_{16}H_{14}O_6$ requires C, 63.2; H, 4.6 per cent).

Dicarbethoxyethylene-desoxyfuroin, prepared from furil (1.5 g.) and ethyl malonate (1.3 g.), crystallised from alcohol in brown microscopic plates. It resembles the foregoing compounds in its properties. (Found: C, 62.2; H, 4.1. $C_{17}H_{16}O_7$ requires C, 61.4; H, 4.7 per cent).

Diacetylene-desoxyfuroin, prepared from furil (1.5 g.) and acetylacetone (0.8 g.), crystallised from alcohol in brown microscopic plates not melting up to 258°. It is soluble in acetone but insoluble in ether and benzene. (Found: C, 66.8; H, 4.01. $C_{15}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 66.1; H, 4.4 per cent).

The condensation product of furil (1.5 g.) and phloroglucinol (1 g.) crystallised from acetone as brown microscopic plates, not melting up to 272°. (Found: C, 65.0; H, 3.2. $C_{16}H_{10}O_6$ requires C, 64.4; H, 3.3 per cent).

Furil Diureine.—The fused mass, obtained by heating an intimate mixture of furil (1 g.) and urea (3 g.) at 200° was repeatedly boiled with alcohol to remove any unreacted urea. It was obtained as a brown crystalline powder not melting up to 295°. It dissolves in sulphuric acid and glacial acetic acid with a black colour. (Found: N, 20.7. $C_{12}H_{10}O_4N_4$ requires N, 20.4 per cent).

Furil Dithioureine, prepared from furil (0.8 g.) and thiourea (2.1 g.) exactly in the same way as in the previous compound, was obtained as a brown crystalline powder, not melting up to 300°. It is insoluble in all the common organic solvents and resembles the previous compound in its properties. (Found: N, 18.3. $C_{12}H_{10}O_2N_4S_2$ requires N, 18.3 per cent).

4:5-Difuryl-2-iminazolone.—An alcoholic solution of furoin (1.7 g.) and urea (0.6 g.) was heated in a sealed tube at 165° for 3 hours. The resultant precipitate was washed repeatedly with boiling alcohol when it was obtained as a brown crystalline powder. It is insoluble in the common organic solvents and does not melt up to 290°. (Found: N, 13.5. $C_{11}H_8O_3N_2$ requires N, 12.9 per cent).

4:5-Difurylthioiminazolone.—It was prepared in the same way as the preceding compound from furoin (1 g.) and thiourea (0.4 g.) and was obtained as a crystalline powder. (Found: N, 12.7. $C_{11}H_8O_2N_2S$ requires N, 12.06 per cent).

2':3'-Difurylindole.—An intimate mixture of furoin (2.4 g.), aniline (4 g.) and aniline hydrochloride (1.6 g.) was heated on the oil-bath for 2½ hours in such a way that the water formed during the reaction could escape but any aniline evaporating flowed back. It was finally washed with water and crystallised from dilute pyridine in brown microscopic plates, not melting up to 285°. (Found: N, 5.8. $C_{16}H_{11}O_2N$ requires N, 5.6 per cent).

2':3'-Difuryl-o-toluidole was prepared from furoin (1.8 g.), *o*-toluidine (2 g.) and *o*-toluidine hydrochloride (0.8 g.) in the same way as the above compound. It is soluble in hot acetone from which it separates in the form of brown microscopic plates, m.p. 201-3°. (Found: N, 5.2. $C_{17}H_{13}O_2N$ requires N, 5.3 per cent).

2':3'-Difuryl-p-toluidole.—The viscous mass obtained by keeping an intimate mixture of furoin (1.5 g.), *p*-toluidine (2 g.) and *p*-toluidine hydrochloride (0.6 g.) in a well-corked flask for 2 days, was heated for 1½ hours at 160°. The resultant precipitate was digested with dilute hydrochloric acid and finally washed with water. It separates from acetone in brown microscopic plates, m.p. 210° (blackening at 180°). It dissolves in alcohol, chloroform and nitrobenzene. (Found: N, 5.6. $C_{17}H_{13}O_2N$ requires N, 5.3 per cent).

2':3'-Difuryl-β-naphthindole.—Furoin (1.6 g.), *β*-naphthylamine (2 g.) and *β*-naphthylamine hydrochloride (0.8 g.) were heated at 175° for 3 hours. The product was digested with dilute hydrochloric acid, washed with water and finally crystallised from acetone in dark brown microscopic plates, m.p. 184-85° (darkening at 170°). It dissolves in alcohol and nitrobenzene. (Found: N, 5.01. $C_{20}H_{13}O_2N$ requires N, 4.6 per cent).

2':3'-Difuryl-α-naphthindole was prepared in the same way from furoin (1.6 g.), *α*-naphthylamine (2 g.) and *α*-naphthylamine hydrochloride (0.8 g.). It crystallises from acetone in brown microscopic plates, not melting up to 240° after which it decomposes. (Found: N, 5.0. $C_{20}H_{13}O_2N$ requires N, 4.6 per cent).